

THE EXPANDED SERIES OF MULTIPLE HARMONIC SUMS AND MULTIPLE ZETA VALUES

KOKI IKEDA

February 24, 2023

Abstract

In this paper, we introduce an explicit expanded series for multiple zeta values. The series is rapidly convergent and defined in a wide region. Additionally, the series yields innumerable identities.

1 Notation

1. Define multiple zeta value as

$$\begin{aligned}\zeta(\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_m) &:= \sum_{1 \leq k_m < k_{m-1} < \dots < k_1} \frac{1}{k_1^{\alpha_1} k_2^{\alpha_2} \dots k_m^{\alpha_m}} \\ &= \sum_{k_m=1}^{\infty} \sum_{k_{m-1}=k_m+1}^{\infty} \dots \sum_{k_1=k_2+1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{k_1^{\alpha_1} k_2^{\alpha_2} \dots k_m^{\alpha_m}}.\end{aligned}$$

In the same way, define finite multiple zeta value as

$$\begin{aligned}\zeta_q(\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_m) &:= \sum_{1 \leq k_m < k_{m-1} < \dots < k_1 \leq q} \frac{1}{k_1^{\alpha_1} k_2^{\alpha_2} \dots k_m^{\alpha_m}} \\ &= \sum_{k_m=1}^q \sum_{k_{m-1}=k_m+1}^q \dots \sum_{k_1=k_2+1}^q \frac{1}{k_1^{\alpha_1} k_2^{\alpha_2} \dots k_m^{\alpha_m}}.\end{aligned}$$

And, $\zeta_q(\alpha_k, \dots, \alpha_{k-1}) := 1$.

2. $\{\alpha\}^m := \underbrace{(\alpha, \dots, \alpha)}_m$.

3. Define difference operator as

$$\Delta_q[f(q)] := f(q+1) - f(q).$$

4. $S_{1st}(\alpha_\beta)$ denotes the signed stirling number of the first kind.

2 The Expansion Formula

Theorem 2.1. *with $\text{Re}(\alpha_1) > 1$ and $q \notin \mathbb{Z}_{<0}$, it follows;*

$$\zeta(\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_m) - \zeta_q(\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_m) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \sum_{j=2}^{m+1} \frac{A_{j,k} \zeta_q(\alpha_j, \dots, \alpha_m)}{k + \alpha_1 - 1} \frac{q!}{(q + k + \alpha_1 - 1)!},$$

$$\text{where } \forall x, \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} A_{j+1,k} \frac{x!}{(x+k+\alpha_1)!} = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{A_{j,k}}{(x+1)^{\alpha_j-1} (k+\alpha_1-1)} \frac{x!}{(x+k+\alpha_1)!} \quad (2 \leq j \leq m),$$

$$A_{2,k} = (-1)^k S_{1st} \binom{k + \alpha_1 - 1}{\alpha_1 - 1}.$$

Proof. Calculating both sides with difference operator will prove that. First, the left side is,

$$\begin{aligned}
\Delta_q[\zeta(\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_m) - \zeta_q(\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_m)] &= -\Delta_q[\zeta_q(\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_m)] \\
&= -\sum_{k_1=1}^{q+1} \sum_{k_2=k_1+1}^{q+1} \cdots \sum_{k_m=k_{m-1}+1}^{q+1} \frac{1}{k_1^{\alpha_m} k_2^{\alpha_{m-1}} \cdots k_m^{\alpha_1}} \\
&\quad + \sum_{k_1=1}^q \sum_{k_2=k_1+1}^q \cdots \sum_{k_m=k_{m-1}+1}^q \frac{1}{k_1^{\alpha_m} k_2^{\alpha_{m-1}} \cdots k_m^{\alpha_1}} \\
&= -\frac{\zeta_q(\alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_m)}{(q+1)^{\alpha_1}}. \tag{1}
\end{aligned}$$

Second, the right side is,

$$\begin{aligned}
&\Delta_q \left[\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \sum_{j=2}^{m+1} \frac{A_{j,k} \zeta_q(\alpha_j, \dots, \alpha_m)}{k + \alpha_1 - 1} \frac{q!}{(q+k+\alpha_1-1)!} \right] \\
&= -\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \sum_{j=2}^{m+1} A_{j,k} \zeta_q(\alpha_j, \dots, \alpha_m) \frac{q!}{(q+k+\alpha_1)!} + \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \sum_{j=2}^m \frac{A_{j,k} \zeta_q(\alpha_j, \dots, \alpha_m)}{(k+\alpha_1-1)(q+1)^{\alpha_j-1}} \frac{q!}{(q+k+\alpha_1)!} \\
&= -\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \zeta_q(\alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_m) (-1)^k \mathcal{S}_{1\text{st}} \left(\begin{matrix} k+\alpha_1-1 \\ \alpha_1-1 \end{matrix} \right) \frac{q!}{(q+k+\alpha_1)!} \\
&\quad - \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \sum_{j=2}^m \left(A_{j+1,k} - \frac{A_{j,k}}{(k+\alpha_1-1)(q+1)^{\alpha_j-1}} \right) \frac{q!}{(q+k+\alpha_1)!} \\
&= -\frac{\zeta_q(\alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_m)}{(q+1)^{\alpha_1}} - \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \sum_{j=2}^m \left(A_{j+1,k} - \frac{A_{j,k}}{(k+\alpha_1-1)(q+1)^{\alpha_j-1}} \right) \frac{q!}{(q+k+\alpha_1)!}. \tag{2}
\end{aligned}$$

Comparing (1) and (2), we get

$$\begin{aligned}
\zeta(\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_m) - \zeta_q(\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_m) &= \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \sum_{j=2}^{m+1} \frac{A_{j,k} \zeta_q(\alpha_j, \dots, \alpha_m)}{k + \alpha_1 - 1} \frac{q!}{(q+k+\alpha_1-1)!} \\
\Leftrightarrow \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} A_{j+1,k} \frac{q!}{(q+k+\alpha_1)!} &= \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{A_{j,k}}{(q+1)^{\alpha_j-1} (k+\alpha_1-1)} \frac{q!}{(q+k+\alpha_1)!} \quad (2 \leq j \leq m), \\
A_{2,k} &= (-1)^k \mathcal{S}_{1\text{st}} \left(\begin{matrix} k+\alpha_1-1 \\ \alpha_1-1 \end{matrix} \right).
\end{aligned}$$

Therefore we have

$$\Delta_q [\zeta(\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_m) - \zeta_q(\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_m)] = \Delta_q \left[\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \sum_{j=2}^{m+1} \frac{A_{j,k} \zeta_q(\alpha_j, \dots, \alpha_m)}{k + \alpha_1 - 1} \frac{q!}{(q+k+\alpha_1-1)!} \right] \tag{3}$$

and

$$\lim_{q \rightarrow \infty} \zeta(\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_m) - \zeta_q(\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_m) = \lim_{q \rightarrow \infty} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \sum_{j=2}^{m+1} \frac{A_{j,k} \zeta_q(\alpha_j, \dots, \alpha_m)}{k + \alpha_1 - 1} \frac{q!}{(q+k+\alpha_1-1)!} = 0. \tag{4}$$

The theorem follows from (3) and (4). $\square$

The expansion formula can be applied for many uses. We have a few examples;

Example 2.1. with $1 < \alpha$,

$$\zeta(\alpha, \{1\}^m) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^k \mathcal{S}_{1\text{st}} \left(\begin{matrix} k+\alpha-1 \\ \alpha-1 \end{matrix} \right)}{(k+\alpha-1)^{m+1} (k+\alpha-1)!}.$$

Proof. In theorem 2.1, let $(q, \alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_{m+1}) \rightarrow (1, \alpha, 1, \dots, 1)$. $\square$

We can see this equation as an analytic continuation for $\zeta(\alpha, \{1\}^m)$. For example,

Example 2.2.

$$\zeta(2, \{1\}^{\frac{1}{2}}) = \zeta \left(\frac{5}{2} \right) = 1.3414 \dots$$

Example 2.3. with $1 < \alpha_1$,

$$\zeta(\alpha_1, \alpha_2) = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^j S_{1st} \left(\frac{j+\alpha_1-1}{\alpha_1-1} \right)}{k^{\alpha_2} (j + \alpha_1 - 1)} \frac{k!}{(k + j + \alpha_1 - 1)!}.$$

Proof.

$$\begin{aligned} \zeta_q(\alpha_1, \alpha_2) &= \sum_{k=1}^q \frac{\zeta_q(\alpha_1) - \zeta_k(\alpha_1)}{k^{\alpha_2}} \\ &= \sum_{k=1}^q \frac{(\zeta(\alpha_1) - \zeta_k(\alpha_1)) - (\zeta(\alpha_1) - \zeta_q(\alpha_1))}{k^{\alpha_2}} \\ &= \sum_{k=1}^q \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^j S_{1st} \left(\frac{j+\alpha_1-1}{\alpha_1-1} \right)}{k^{\alpha_2} (j + \alpha_1 - 1)} \left(\frac{k!}{(k + j + \alpha_1 - 1)!} - \frac{q!}{(q + j + \alpha_1 - 1)!} \right) \end{aligned}$$

Let $q \rightarrow \infty$, we obtain

$$\zeta(\alpha_1, \alpha_2) = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^j S_{1st} \left(\frac{j+\alpha_1-1}{\alpha_1-1} \right)}{k^{\alpha_2} (j + \alpha_1 - 1)} \frac{k!}{(k + j + \alpha_1 - 1)!}.$$

□

For instance,

Example 2.4.

$$\zeta(3) = \zeta(2, 1) = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \frac{(k-1)!(j-1)!}{j(k+j)!}.$$

Example 2.5.

$$\frac{3}{4}\zeta(4) = \zeta(2, 2) = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \frac{(k-1)!(j-1)!}{jk(k+j)!}.$$

References

- [1] Hanamichi Kawamura, Takumi Maesaka, Shin-ichiro Seki *Multivariable connected sums and multiple polylogarithms.* [arXiv](#)

Koki Ikeda E-mail: kouki_21s1101579@nnn.ed.jp

If the e-mail above is invalid: koki0337.1229s@gmail.com